

PAINTING

CULTURAL IDENTITY OF CHINESE INTANGIBLE HERITAGE AND THE INTEGRATION OF DIGITAL CREATIVE TECHNOLOGY: WUHU IRON PAINTING

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ABSTRACT

Background: Wuhu iron painting, a nationally recognized intangible cultural heritage of China, reflects a unique fusion of artistry and craftsmanship with profound cultural value. Nevertheless, in the face of modernization, this traditional art form faces challenges such as declining public awareness, limited industrial integration, and an aging artisan workforce. **Purpose:** This study explores how digital creative technologies and educational innovations can jointly safeguard and revitalize Wuhu iron painting. **Methods:** Employing a qualitative and exploratory design, the research integrates cultural-technical analysis, case study evaluation, and framework development. Case studies such as the Tianmen Smoke and Waves digital collection illustrate how virtual simulation, interactive design, and blockchain authentication enhance cultural visibility and user engagement. **Results:** Beyond digital innovation, this paper highlights the pivotal role of teacher training and curriculum development in sustaining heritage transmission. Teacher education programs incorporating intangible cultural heritage and digital pedagogy equip educators with the capacity to integrate Wuhu iron painting into classrooms, while curriculum frameworks at school and vocational levels foster students' cultural literacy, creativity, and practical skills. **Conclusion:** The findings emphasize a holistic strategy combining resource-based digital platforms, apprenticeship-based talent cultivation, immersive learning centers, teacher professional development, and curriculum integration. This integrated approach not only preserves the authenticity of Wuhu iron painting but also transforms it into an educational and cultural resource that supports cultural sustainability, vocational training, and international dissemination.

KEY WORDS

Wuhu Iron Painting, Intangible Cultural Heritage, Digital Preservation, Cultural Identity, Innovation, User Experience.

INTRODUCTION

Chinese intangible cultural heritage serves as a testament to the lengthy history and rich culture of the Chinese nation, embodying a significant cultural legacy and national memory (Li et al., 2024). Iron painting, historically known as “Iron Flower,” is a distinctive craft from Wuhu City, Anhui Province, recognized as one of the national intangible cultural heritages. It holds an essential place in Chinese traditional culture due to its unique artistic style and skilled craftsmanship (McIntyre et al., 2023). Iron painting involves creating images from wrought iron wire and iron plates. The Wuhu iron smelting industry has developed since ancient times, earning the reputation of “the iron to Wuhu since the steel.” Wuhu iron painting and forging craft is built on this foundation. During the Kangxi era of the Qing Dynasty, Wuhu Iron Painting became self-contained and gradually gained international fame. In 2006, Wuhu Iron Painting Forging Craft was recognized as part of the first group of national intangible cultural heritage items by the State Council. Wuhu Iron Painting exemplifies a distinct artistic style, employing a hammer as a brush, iron as the medium for ink, and wrought iron as the medium. Yet, amidst the swift advancements of modern society, intangible cultural heritage encounters numerous challenges, including issues with inheritance and a lack of recognition. Finding effective ways to preserve and innovate this national intangible cultural heritage within today’s context is a pressing concern (Gulyaeva, 2021; Wang, 2023).

Concurrently, digital creative technology presents fresh opportunities for the preservation and transmission of intangible cultural heritage. By leveraging digital techniques, it becomes possible to broaden the reach and visibility of intangible cultural heritage, thereby strengthening its cultural identity and enhancing its social impact.

The paper analyzes how digital technology can preserve and enhance the cultural identity of Wuhu iron painting by examining its core techniques iron forging, quenching, and lacquering within a user-centered design framework that incorporates multi-sensory engagement. Case studies such as the Tianmen Smoke and Waves digital collection show the effectiveness of digitization in conserving and promoting the craft. The study proposes a digital strategy to tackle challenges of talent inheritance, limited exposure, weak industrial integration, and inadequate legal protection, offering new insights for revitalizing traditional craftsmanship.

RELATED WORKS

Application of Digital Technologies in Cultural Heritage Preservation

Introduce a concept aimed at sustaining cultural

heritage digitally, especially in settings with insufficient infrastructure for long-term use of digital assets (Paschalidou, Fafet, & Milios, 2022). Their proposed system of distributed digital preservation expands the digital archive while granting access to archived data. This system aligns with the extended Open Archival Information System (OAIS) reference model and is articulated through the External-Internal OAIS (OO-IO). It aims to support these institutions in preserving cultural heritage through practical long-term preservation and access strategies (Fatorić & Seekamp, 2017).

According to Ahmed, Alfaqheri and Sadka (2021) discussed the significance of digital image restoration techniques in safeguarding cultural heritage by introducing a new two-stage restoration method. This method focuses on recognizing surface details in paintings to fill in and restore damaged sections of digital images. Their imaging restoration approach combines Delaunay triangular interpolation with example-based restoration techniques to enhance the preservation of digital images of cultural heritage (Ahmed et al., 2021; Amusa et al., 2024). Additionally, Mironova et al. (2020), examined the Digital Surface Hyper heritage method, which is an academic initiative designed to map the topography of art paintings. Utilizing high-resolution roughness and imaging technology, this method aims to uncover the topographic characteristics of painting surfaces, offering fresh insights into the conservation and restoration of artworks (Mironova et al., 2020).

Innovative Approaches to Merging Digital Technology and Traditional Culture

Ma and Wang (2021) investigated how modern information technology can aid in the conservation and transmission of iron painting, an intangible cultural heritage. They highlighted the reconstruction of iron painting works through information gathering techniques, aimed at ensuring lasting preservation. Furthermore, the iron painting information database’s user data correlation feature can align with the varying interests and preferences of users interested in different aspects of intangible heritage, thereby facilitating the digital reconstruction and enduring preservation of iron painting works (Ma & Wang, 2021). According to Zhou (2024) proposed utilizing digital art elements to enhance traditional cultural design methods. This approach encompasses technologies such as digital-assisted design, image processing techniques, and real-time tracking and interaction within 3D tracking and mixed reality environments. The goal is to create a digitally supported experience of cultural symbols and

optimize the creative design process in the cultural sector, thereby enriching the digital interaction with cultural symbols.

Meanwhile, Cheng, Liang and Li (2020) employed research methods including field surveys, interviews, and participant observation to investigate the inheritance and development paths of traditional culture in today's context. The findings revealed that Wuhu Iron Painting has surged into the modern age by integrating cross-border digital technologies. It has launched innovative cultural forms, such as digital iron painting collections, effectively attracting younger consumers and providing fresh perspectives on the inheritance and innovation of traditional culture. Thus, considering the artistic traits of Wuhu iron painting, its inheritance and development should focus on enhancing network publicity and social promotion, as well as boosting the creation and innovation of iron painting products (Cheng et al., 2020).

The Impact of Digital Technologies on Promoting and Sharing Cultural Heritage

According to Todorova-Ekmekci (2021) examines various media and marketing strategies for the digital presentation and promotion of cultural heritage, showcasing the historical and cultural heritage of different countries through digital tools. This includes video showcases of 3D models, interactive photos and videos paired with objects, as well as interactive displays, games, online tours, and live social media events, all highlighting the critical role of digitization in enhancing the visibility and appeal of cultural heritage (Todorova-Ekmekci, 2021). According to Lian and Xie (2024) compelling study utilizes Cite Space tools to investigate the evolution and future directions in digital cultural heritage research, pinpointing research hotspots and forecasting future trends. It underscores the significance of transnational and interdisciplinary collaboration. Additionally, while current DCH research focuses on nations with significant national power, there is a call for future research to concentrate more on cultural heritage regions and to foster transnational and interdisciplinary initiatives. The use of virtual reality, augmented reality, and other interactive digital tools also enriches experiences related to cultural heritage (Lian & Xie, 2024).

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a qualitative and exploratory research design to investigate how digital creative technologies can support the preservation and revitalization of Wuhu iron painting as an intangible cultural heritage. The research was structured

around three interrelated dimensions, namely cultural-technical analysis, case study evaluation, and framework development, allowing for a comprehensive exploration of both the traditional craftsmanship and its transformation in the digital era. Data were derived from a combination of primary and secondary sources. Archival and historical documents provided insights into the origins, techniques, and symbolic features of Wuhu iron painting, while project reports, sales records, and institutional publications offered detailed accounts of digitization initiatives such as the Tianmen Smoke and Waves digital collection. In addition, scholarly literature on cultural heritage preservation, user experience design, and digital innovation was consulted to establish the theoretical foundation of the study (Lian & Xie, 2024).

The study employed a qualitative and exploratory design with a three-step data collection process that connected traditional craftsmanship to emerging digital practices. First, a cultural and technical analysis reviewed forging, quenching, and lacquering techniques, identifying the elements that form the cultural identity of Wuhu iron painting. Second, a case study evaluation examined digitization initiatives such as blockchain authentication, interactive virtual simulations, and digital art collectibles to demonstrate how technology is reshaping cultural heritage practices. Third, a thematic synthesis integrated insights from both traditional and digital contexts, highlighting how cultural identity and user engagement can be enhanced through innovative applications of technology.

Data analysis adopted a thematic and comparative approach by mapping traditional artistic features including red satin forging, cold forging, and lacquer finishing against digital preservation tools such as immersive simulation, emotional design layers, and interactive media. To ensure rigor and reliability, methodological triangulation was applied through cross-referencing findings from scholarly literature, case-based evidence, and expert assessments reported in institutional documents. This approach not only strengthened the validity of the results but also ensured that the proposed framework is both theoretically grounded and practically applicable to cultural heritage preservation and innovation.

THE CONSTRUCTION OF CULTURAL IDENTITY IN THE WUHU IRON PAINTING FORGING CRAFT PERFORMANCE AND ITS ARTISTIC CHARACTERISTICS

Wuhu Iron Painting is crafted from low-carbon steel and features a design inspired by traditional Chinese painting. It captures the essence of the

artwork through processes like cutting, forging, shaping, joining, and lacquering. The performance of iron painting is divided into three main stages: iron forging, quenching, and lacquering. The iron forging stage focuses on shaping the “form”. It is further divided into overall modeling, detailed performance, and picture-level elements, as well as other vital components that convey the artistic style and meaning of the iron painting. The quenching and lacquering stages represent the “color” in iron paintings, playing a crucial role in creating tone and atmosphere, both of which are fundamental to the distinctive artistic features of iron paintings.

Artistic Features of Wuhu Iron Painting Craftsmanship

Wrought iron technology refers to the forging process used in creating iron artworks, where craftsmen apply various techniques to shape and texture the material. A key method is red satin, which involves heating mild steel to make it more ductile and easier to shape. This process is essential for crafting complex forms and detailed textures, as it allows significant shape transformation and enhances the three-dimensional quality of the

artwork. Artisans often begin by modularizing designs and then using red satin to shape the iron according to these models.

In contrast, cold forging does not involve heating. It requires even, gentle hammering to gradually shape the iron. This method demands extreme precision and patience, as the hammer strokes must be consistent to avoid damaging the material. Cold forging results in a polished finish and strengthens the iron’s hardness and toughness. However, it is better suited for simpler forms or for refining surfaces already forged with red satin. While red satin emphasizes expressive texture and form, cold forging adds subtlety and smoothness, making the two techniques complementary in the creation of intricate and artistic ironwork. Both require a high level of craftsmanship and reflect the traditional artistry behind wrought iron painting. As a tangible representation of the fusion of Wuhu iron forging techniques with Chinese cultural symbols, this work features the magpie and plum blossom as symbols of good fortune and blessings as refer to Figure 1. This motif not only showcases the artisans’ artistic skill in crafting delicate details but also represents cultural values passed down through generations.

Figure 1: “Magpies on Plum Blossoms” – a Wuhu Iron Painting Created within the Virtual Simulation System.

Hardened Lacquering Process and Artistic Characteristics of Iron Painting

The quenching process of traditional iron painting is designed to enhance the steel’s high strength and toughness after red satin, thereby preventing the iron painting module from falling off over time. Later, under the guidance of national arts and crafts master Chu Jinxia, quenching was given a new meaning: the quenching process can enrich the expressive colors of iron paintings. Lacquering refers to the process of applying hot-baked rosin

cypress oil as a lacquer on iron paintings to prevent rusting and corrosion, while also increasing the gloss and revealing the black color. With the advancement of time, rosin cypress oil has been replaced by modern paint, and there has been a slight change in the painting technique. When the entire surface is coated uniformly using the traditional lacquering method, it may give off a sensation of excessive heaviness in craftsmanship and a lack of ambiance. Thus, skilled artisans intelligently modify the lacquer’s thickness to

match the painting’s hierarchical requirements. Table 1 showcases the artistic and cultural identity performance of Wuhu iron painting craft; these facets are interconnected and reinforce one another, together forming the distinctive allure and value of

Wuhu iron painting’s cultural legacy. Enhancing the recognition of cultural identity elements will aid in improving the public’s awareness of the Wuhu iron painting forging technique, consequently supporting its preservation and continuation.

Table 1: Performance of Wuhu Iron Painting Craftsmanship and Artistic Cultural Identity.

Cultural Identity Elements	Concrete Content	The Relationship between Wuhu Iron Painting Craftsmanship and Artistic Features
Process performance	Iron forging process	Responsible for shaping the “form” of iron painting is the foundation of the artistic style and artistic expression of iron painting.
	Red satin	Core technique, forged after heating, with good extensibility, suitable for complex shapes, reflecting the three-dimensional sense and texture effect of iron painting.
	Cold forging	Non heating hammer forging requires gentle and even force to create a delicate and soft artistic style, enhancing the hardness and toughness of iron parts.
	Fire connection	Connecting the various parts of the iron painting to ensure a stable overall structure is an indispensable part of iron painting production.
	Quenching process	Traditionally, enhancing the strength and toughness of iron paintings to prevent detachment; In modern times, quenching enriches the colors of iron paintings and enhances their artistic expression.
	Painting process	Replace traditional rosin and asphalt with modern paint, adjust the thickness of the paint according to the level of the image, increase glossiness, prevent rust, and enhance the artistic effect by revealing black color.
Artistic features	rhythmic vitality	The red satin craftsmanship endows iron paintings with a brush and ink style reminiscent of traditional Chinese painting, showcasing a unique artistic charm.
	Accurate design	The cold forging process ensures precise iron painting shapes, rich details, and showcases the exquisite craftsmanship of the craftsmen.
	Rich colors	The innovative application of quenching technology has enriched and diversified the colors of iron paintings, enhancing their artistic expression.
	Glossiness and Durability	The painting process not only increases the glossiness of iron paintings, but also improves their durability, enabling them to be preserved for a long time.
Cultural Value	Historical Inheritance	Wuhu iron painting, as a traditional handicraft, carries rich historical and cultural connotations and is a symbol of regional culture.
	Artistic innovation	The continuous innovation of forging, quenching, painting and other processes has promoted the development of Wuhu iron painting art, making it more in line with modern aesthetic needs.
	Craftsmanship spirit	The production process of Wuhu iron paintings contains the wisdom and sweat of craftsmen, reflecting their persistent pursuit of art and the spirit of excellence.

THE APPLICATION OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGY IN PROTECTING AND INHERITING WUHU IRON PAINTING AND FORGING TECHNIQUES

The Importance of user Experience in Digital Design

The concept of user experience first emerged in the realm of human-computer interaction with electronic products. It gradually became a widely used term in the design and evaluation of major websites and various applications. Nowadays, numerous definitions of UX exist worldwide; however, most scholars agree that UX should be user-centered (Chouki et al., 2021). The International Organization for Standardization defines user experience as the user’s perception and reaction to the use or intended use of an application, encompassing their emotions, preferences, beliefs, comfort, behaviors, and outcomes before, during, and after using the application. User experience is inherently subjective, reflecting the individual’s presentation of, experience with, and attitudes toward the system.

UX is dynamic because it evolves in response to the environment, as illustrated by the five elements of UX in Figure 1. The first layer, the strategy layer, encompasses product goals and user needs. By conducting thorough research in the initial stages,

product goals can align closely with users’ actual needs this alignment is the most fundamental and essential aspect of user experience design (Serafeim, 2020). The second layer is the scope layer, which focuses on achieving the product’s strategic objectives by outlining specific services and defining the functional boundaries of its requirements. The third layer is the structural layer, which refers to the design of the relationship between the product’s information architecture and content. This layer determines the form and order of user interaction after prioritizing captured user requirements and integrating these dispersed fragments into a cohesive whole. The fourth layer is the framework layer, which focuses on implementing a detailed, step-by-step design based on the requirements of the structure layer. The fifth layer is the performance layer, which is the ultimate goal of user experience design, where users develop an intuitive understanding of the product based on the design of this layer. The final design is presented through the integration of content, function, and art, achieved through exceptional design based on the first four layers.

The Five Elements of User Experience and Emotionality

Emotional design also focuses on the user

experience aspect of a product's design. The concept, introduced by American psychologist Donald Norman, emphasizes the emotional impact of design and is categorized into three levels: the instinctive layer, the behavioral layer, and the reflective layer, as illustrated in Figure 2. The instinctive layer refers to the user's initial sensory

experience, highlighting the visual appeal of the product. It connects with the user's consciousness and emotions, making the design attractive and resonating with their feelings. This blend of aesthetics and functionality enhances the overall value of the user experience.

Figure 2: Five Elements of User Experience.

The behavioral layer of the design experience primarily focuses on product performance and human-computer interaction, based on users' behavioral habits. This alignment enhances the product's functionality to resonate with users' thought processes, leading to efficient human-computer interaction and providing users with a sense of pleasure during the experience. The reflection layer emphasizes the meanings and connotations associated with the product, aiming

for the product's rationality to resonate with users at a deeper level through design. This allows individuals to reflect on their self-image and the embodiment of value, considering their emotional needs, and ensuring that their hearts, minds, emotions, and spirits are satisfied on a deeper level. These three layers influence one another in design, and the central aim is to ensure that the user's experience with the product remains enjoyable as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Three Levels of Emotional Design.

Interaction Design of Iron Painting Products

In the information age, the Wuhu iron painting and forging craft faces the challenge of homogenization and is actively seeking paths for transformation and development. In the context of a new media landscape, this craft is transitioning from traditional physical advertising to an online virtual reality data domain. It incorporates four essential areas of basic interaction design: visual interaction, auditory interaction, action interaction, and symbolic-

emotional interaction. Table 2 details the specific contents and characteristics of various interaction design levels. The Wuhu iron painting and forging craft has evolved from a two-dimensional plane to three-dimensional dynamics in its promotional materials. Utilizing panoramic photography and three-dimensional dynamic technology, it creates a virtual reality platform that forges a strong connection with the audience's sensory experiences, thereby significantly enhancing the industry's influence on Wuhu iron painting.

Table 2: Content and Characteristics of Different Interaction Design Levels.

Interaction Design Level	Segmented Content	Description and Characteristics
Visual Form	Static interaction	The art of iron painting emphasizes the static beauty and cultural connotations of iron painting through colors, decorative patterns, character shapes, and font styles [18-19].
	Dynamic interaction	Using pictures and patterns as the main subject, vividly present the forging process of iron paintings, such as the dynamic display of "Welcoming Guests with Pine", and appreciate the charm of iron paintings from multiple perspectives [20].
Auditory interaction	Background sound	Create an atmosphere, like the sound of wind, rain, thunder and lightning throughout the four seasons.
	Bian Bai Yin	Provide historical background introduction, work information, etc. to enhance understanding.
	System sound	Feedback information, such as the sound effect when clicking a button.
Action interaction	Gesture interaction	Perform visual operations through gestures, such as clicking, sliding, etc.
	Physical interaction	Simulate the forging process of iron painting with body movements to enhance participation.
	Interactive experience	Video guidance, simulated operations, enhance fun.
Symbolic emotional interaction	Innovative Design	Design iron paintings that embody the aesthetic of the new era, taking into account the hot topics of the times.
	Color Style	Using modern color combinations to enhance visual appeal.
	Symbol usage	Incorporating modern symbolic elements to enrich the connotation of the work.
	Font design	The combination of calligraphy art and iron painting showcases a unique aesthetic.
	Emotional resonance	Enhance visitors' understanding and emotional connection to iron painting culture through design.

Wuhu Iron Painting Forging Craft Digitization Project Case

Iron painting digital collectibles have emerged as a modern cultural innovation, offering a fresh, youthful experience that has captured widespread public interest. Unlike traditional artworks, these collectibles are intangible, existing as limited-edition digital cultural assets. Their core features such as unique serial numbers, permanent storage, non-replicability, and tamper resistance have made them increasingly valued in the digital art market.

In July 2022, the Yangtze River Delta Information and Intelligence Innovation Research Institute, KEDA Xunfei Co., Ltd., and the Wuhu Iron Painting Association collaborated with traditional Wuhu iron painting artisans to launch a digital art collection project. These digital collectibles integrate traditional iron forging techniques with modern digital platforms as illustrated in Table

3, inspired by Chinese cultural elements such as Li Bai's poem "Wangtianmen Mountain" and the Wuhu landscape "Tianmen Smoke Waves." Works like Tianmen Smoke Waves, Pine Eagle, and Fuchun Mountain Residence Map were released as 3D digital collections. A total of 5,000 units were sold out within a minute, generating 120,000 yuan in revenue.

On June 20, 2023, another release featuring 1,900 digital iron painting collectibles created by seven recognized artisans was launched via the StarDay App and similarly sold out quickly. Each piece utilized blockchain technology to issue a unique digital certificate, ensuring its authenticity and identity in the digital space. These initiatives have greatly enhanced the visibility and preservation of Wuhu iron painting, expanding its influence within the digital collectibles space and promoting its cultural value through innovative technologies.

Table 3: Digitization Project of Wuhu Iron Painting Forging Techniques.

Implementation Time	Partner	Digital Collection Name	Issuance Quantity	Sales Progress	Revenue Situation
December 15, 2022	Yangtze River Delta Information Intelligence Innovation Research Institute, Nie Chuanchun	Tianmen Smoke and Waves, Pine Eagle, Dwelling in Fuchun Mountain, etc	5000	Within ten minutes, it was emptied	120000 yuan
June 20, 2023	Yangtze River Delta Information Intelligence Innovation Research Institute, seven inheritors of Wuhu Iron Painting Forging Technology	Collaborative Iron Painting Digital Collection	1900	Sold out within minutes	100000 yuan

ANALYSIS OF THE DEVELOPMENT DILEMMA IN WUHU IRON PAINTING FORGING CRAFT

The successful case study of the digitization project for Wuhu iron painting forging craft illustrates how digital technology has injected new life into traditional art, enhancing its dissemination and preservation in modern society. Wuhu iron painting has a glorious history, but it has inevitably encountered the challenges of transition. Now, driven by societal interests, the varied quality of iron painting has come to rely on state intervention and support. Concurrently, with the rapid advancement of science and technology, the introduction of new materials and the rise of new handicrafts have significantly impacted the development of Wuhu iron painting.

Fragmentation and Inadequate Resource Sharing

Wuhu iron painting was once popular in the 1980s, supported by the government and recognized both in China and abroad. But in the 1990s, its popularity declined due to social changes. Today, knowledge and skills about iron painting are scattered across individuals and organizations, with no central digital resource to preserve and share them.

This makes it hard for people to learn the craft, pass it down, or promote it widely. To help the industry grow, it's important to modernize by combining traditional techniques with digital tools and online promotion. Some efforts are already being made to raise awareness, but a stronger connection between Wuhu iron painting and modern media is needed to ensure its future.

Insufficient Talent Training System

One of the greatest challenges facing Wuhu iron painting is the shortage of new talent to continue the craft. Most current artisans are elderly, and only a small number of young people are entering the field, even though partnerships between schools and enterprises have been established. Historical records documenting the techniques are often lost, poorly preserved, or inaccessible, further weakening the transfer of knowledge. While the traditional master-apprentice system maintains authenticity, it is restricted by the small number of apprentices it can support and the slow pace of learning. At the same time, vocational education still lacks structured programs and qualified teachers dedicated to training new artisans. Broader social trends also contribute to the problem: many young people prefer fast-paced urban lifestyles over long hours in a workshop, and some show little interest in traditional culture.

Even when students pursue iron painting, they often do so for commercial reasons rather than cultural commitment, making it difficult to foster genuine passion and long-term dedication.

Limited Awareness and Interactive Participation

Another significant challenge in preserving Wuhu iron painting lies in the limited public awareness and lack of active participation. This issue is often aggravated by the low quality of some products, which diminishes public interest and satisfaction, thereby weakening overall engagement. Since awareness, satisfaction, and participation are closely interconnected, insufficient recognition directly reduces the craft's visibility and cultural influence. At present, public knowledge of Wuhu iron painting remains minimal, resulting in a small market and a limited audience. Promotional efforts are largely confined to offline exhibitions and word-of-mouth, which restrict their reach and impact. Although emerging technologies such as virtual reality have been introduced to create interactive experiences, these initiatives are still at an early stage and lack the development needed to engage audiences on a larger scale. Without stronger communication systems, broader visibility, and coordinated support from both government and industry, it will remain difficult to foster public enthusiasm, encourage active participation, and ensure the long-term preservation of this cultural heritage.

Lack of Adequate Industrial Integration and Innovation

The development of Wuhu iron painting remains constrained by its reliance on handmade reproduction with limited artistic variety. Most works are based on fixed models, prioritizing quality and quantity to ensure completion but offering little room for innovation. While current products largely come from senior master craftsmen, the absence of a systematic teaching framework has left younger learners without structured guidance, resulting in a lack of creativity and new development. Consequently, the craft has preserved only its most fundamental techniques and struggles to expand beyond a small market.

Industrial integration with other sectors such as tourism, education, science, and technology has not yet been sufficiently developed, and cross-disciplinary cooperation remains weak. The innovation of iron painting products also falls short of meeting the increasingly diverse and personalized preferences of modern consumers. Traditional works are often presented in a single artistic form, disconnected from contemporary

lifestyles and aesthetic trends, which limits both their appeal and commercial potential. These challenges restrict the market scale of Wuhu iron painting and prevent it from achieving sustainable growth, highlighting the urgent need for stronger integration, innovation, and modernization strategies.

THE CULTURAL IDENTITY OF WUHU IRON PAINTING AND THE INTEGRATION AND INHERITANCE STRATEGIES OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGY

The digital inheritance countermeasures of Wuhu iron painting encompass various aspects, including resource-based construction, talent training programs, the establishment of interactive experience centers, and the removal of industrial barriers, among others. The Wuhu iron painting integration inheritance strategy system is depicted in Figure 4. Through collaboration among government, industry, enterprises, and educational institutions, a digital resource base for iron painting

is created, leveraging multiple platforms. At the same time, the content is dynamically adjusted to cater to a diverse array of user groups.

Leverage vocational education foundations to implement a modern apprenticeship system, develop systematic training programs, and cultivate professionals through collaboration between schools and enterprises, along with integrating enrollment and recruitment. Create an interactive experience center for iron painting art that utilizes virtual simulation technology to provide a comprehensive virtual production experience, promoting the popularization and dissemination of these skills. Break down industrial barriers by merging iron painting with diverse cultural elements and the tourism industry to safeguard intellectual property rights and encourage the preservation and inheritance of iron painting. Together, these strategies form a comprehensive system for the digital preservation of Wuhu iron painting, providing strong support for the conservation and development of this art form.

Figure 4: Wuhu Iron Painting Integration and Inheritance Strategy System.

Collaboration between Government, Industry, Enterprises, Schools, and Quadripartite to Create the Iron Painting Digital Resource Library Mechanism

With strong support from the Department of Intangible Cultural Heritage under the Ministry of Culture and Tourism, Anhui Technical College of Mechanical and Electrical Engineering has led a major initiative to preserve and promote Wuhu iron painting through the creation of a shared digital teaching resource platform. Anchored by cultural and educational bases such as the Vocational Education Base, the Inheritance and Innovation Base, and the Research Institute, this project brings together local colleges, universities, industries, and government

agencies to collaboratively develop and update high-quality teaching materials. Experts, professors, and skilled artisans contribute to the production of content that reflects new products, techniques, and technologies, ensuring that the resource base remains relevant, innovative, and future-oriented. Designed to support flexible and personalized learning, the digital library enables students to study independently, assists teachers in customizing and enriching their lessons, and extends benefits to industry employees, adult learners, and community members seeking to enhance their skills. By integrating the strengths of government, business, and educational institutions, the platform establishes a comprehensive hub for teaching and learning that revives, sustains, and

strengthens the cultural legacy of Wuhu iron painting.

Systematic Execution of the Talent Training and Development Program for Iron Painting and Forging Techniques

In 2015, Anhui Technical College of Mechanical and Electrical Engineering inaugurated a vocational education base for Wuhu iron painting, positioning itself as one of the first modern apprenticeship pilot units in China. To preserve this intangible cultural heritage, the college established a Professional Teaching and Research Office, identified the essential knowledge and skills for the craft, and developed comprehensive teaching resources that include curriculum frameworks, lesson plans, training methods, assessment systems, and school enterprise cooperation agreements. The program was promoted broadly to ensure that students understood the expectations and requirements before enrolling, with measures such as leadership structures, tripartite agreements among apprentices, schools, and enterprises, as well as accident and liability insurance. Once implemented, the apprenticeship combined theoretical classroom instruction with hands-on training guided by enterprise masters, embedding workplace culture into each stage of learning. A quality assurance system, including regular evaluations and enterprise feedback, was introduced to maintain high standards. This framework not only enhances students' technical proficiency and vocational literacy but also nurtures their cultural commitment, providing a systematic and standardized approach to talent cultivation and the long-term preservation of Wuhu iron painting.

Develop a Comprehensive Wuhu Iron Painting Art Interactive Experience and Inheritance Center

The rapid growth of network technology and virtual reality has introduced new opportunities for preserving and transmitting Wuhu iron painting, offering immersive, interactive, and engaging experiences that bring traditional craftsmanship into the digital age. To harness this potential, an interactive experience center has been established to showcase the forging techniques of iron painting through virtual simulations that replicate key processes such as forging, welding, drilling, filing, shaping, rust treatment, and lacquer application. This system allows audiences to engage directly with the production process, enhancing their understanding of both its artistic and technical dimensions. By integrating elements of artistic conception, material application, modeling design, and cultural symbolism, the platform encourages active learning, creativity, and emotional connection. Participants can record and share their experiences through digital

platforms and social media, extending the reach of this cultural heritage to wider audiences. Supported by high-speed network services, the initiative builds an interactive educational environment accessible to schools, communities, and industries, thereby cultivating a broad and participatory learning network. Through this approach, Wuhu iron painting is transformed into both a cultural and educational resource, enabling wider public engagement and supporting the sustainable preservation of its traditional forging methods.

Comprehensive Promotion of the Iron Painting Industry and Multi-Cultural Integration Development Strategy

Integrating Wuhu iron painting into the broader development of the city fosters mutually beneficial connections with cultural, creative, and tourism industries while supporting its long-term preservation. By capitalizing on Wuhu's position as a tourist destination, an ecological industry chain can be established that links cultural heritage with tourism, allowing iron painting to become a core component of protective and sustainable tourism. Drawing on China's successful models of theme parks, festival tourism, museum development, and non-heritage products, Wuhu has the opportunity to design innovative approaches such as family-oriented cultural tours, student study trips, and live performance activities where visitors can actively participate in the production process. Collaborations with cultural influencers and the creation of refined cultural creative products can further enhance public interest and market appeal.

At the same time, increasing visibility through museums, creative parks, and prominent public spaces such as plazas and transportation hubs can help embed iron painting more deeply into public consciousness. Institutional support has also strengthened with the introduction of Wuhu's first local legislation, the Wuhu Iron Painting Protection and Development Regulations, which provides a legal foundation for heritage preservation. To maximize its impact, however, the government must actively promote these regulations, ensure law enforcement, and reinforce awareness of intellectual property rights and cultural safety. Taken together, these strategies enhance the visibility, attractiveness, and protection of Wuhu iron painting while ensuring its inheritance and continued vitality as a valued element of intangible cultural heritage.

Teacher Training and Curriculum Development for Heritage Education

The sustainable preservation of Wuhu iron painting requires not only technological innovation and

industrial collaboration but also systematic efforts in education through teacher training and curriculum integration. Teachers act as cultural mediators who connect traditional craftsmanship with contemporary learning, and therefore their preparation should include modules on intangible cultural heritage, digital pedagogy, and culturally responsive teaching. Both pre-service and in-service training can enhance teachers' capacity to design interactive lessons that incorporate digital resources such as virtual simulations, augmented reality, and online repositories. Collaborative workshops involving master artisans and educators provide teachers with authentic cultural knowledge while strengthening their pedagogical and technical competencies.

At the same time, curriculum development ensures that Wuhu iron painting is embedded into formal and vocational education in ways that balance knowledge, skills, and values. Students can learn the history and symbolism of the craft, practice forging and design through simulations or workshops, and develop cultural pride and appreciation of craftsmanship. Competency-based curricula, combining theory, practice, and digital innovation, enable students to demonstrate cultural understanding alongside creative and vocational skills. By aligning teacher training with curriculum innovation, Wuhu iron painting is transformed from a traditional craft into an educational resource that fosters cultural sustainability, creativity, and lifelong learning.

CONCLUSION

Wuhu iron painting embodies unique artistic value and cultural significance, representing not only a craft but also a living expression of Chinese cultural identity. Its survival in the context of rapid modernization depends on both innovative digital preservation methods and structured educational strategies. The combination of traditional techniques such as forging, quenching, and lacquering with digital technologies like virtual simulation, blockchain authentication, and interactive design has already demonstrated strong potential in revitalizing this heritage and expanding its visibility. However, safeguarding Wuhu iron painting also requires robust human capital development. Teacher training and curriculum integration are essential pathways to ensure that the knowledge, skills, and values of this craft are transmitted across generations. By equipping teachers with digital pedagogy, culturally responsive teaching methods, and co-teaching opportunities with master artisans, education systems can create a sustainable model for heritage transmission. Likewise, embedding Wuhu iron painting into school and vocational curricula

strengthens students' cultural literacy, nurtures creativity, and promotes interdisciplinary learning that bridges tradition with innovation.

The findings of this study therefore suggest a holistic framework for the preservation and dissemination of Wuhu iron painting: one that combines digital innovation, industrial collaboration, teacher professional development, and curriculum design. This integrated approach not only protects an invaluable intangible cultural heritage but also transforms it into an educational and cultural resource with global relevance. Moving forward, policymakers, educators, and cultural practitioners should collaborate to institutionalize heritage education and expand the application of digital creative technologies, ensuring that Wuhu iron painting continues to inspire and thrive in both local and international contexts.

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